

The mushroom spider *Phoroncidia eburnea* (Simon, 1895) (Araneae: Theridiidae) from South Africa

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ABSTRACT: *Phoroncidia eburnea* (Simon, 1895), a species described from Transvaal, South Africa. It has since been recorded in Swaziland and in the provinces of KwaZulu-Natal, Eastern Cape, and Western Cape in South Africa. The general morphology of the species is discussed based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

INTRODUCTION

During surveys of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), large numbers of theridiids were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), but due to a lack of taxonomic resolution, several species could not be identified. Between the sampled theridiid material, there were several specimens recognised as members of *Phoroncidia*. The genus *Phoroncidia* Westwood, 1835 is represented by 84 species (World Spider Catalog, 2025). Eleven species are known from Africa and three from South Africa.

One of the South African species sampled from the northern and central areas in South Africa keyed out as *Phoroncidia eburnea* (Simon, 1895). The female of *P. eburnea* was described as *Ulesanis eburnean* from Transvaal, no exact locality. That was some 130 years ago, and since then, little has been reported on the species. The general morphology of the species is discussed based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status.

TAXONOMY

Phoroncidia eburnea (Simon, 1895)

Ulesanis eburnea Simon, 1895: 147 (Df).

Phoroncidia eburnea Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021: 56;
Dippenaar-Schoeman. 2023: 139.

Description: Female TL 3 mm. Carapace fawn, margin darker; it is as wide as long; anterior blunt with eyes slightly protruding (Figs 2 & 11). Eyes: median eyes further from each other than from lateral eyes (Fig. 11); they occupy an area much wider than long, narrower in front than behind; eye field protrudes forward, overhanging the clypeus (Figs 5 & 10); median eyes larger than lateral eyes (Fig. 11). Sternum dark brown, somewhat smooth (Figs 13 & 14). Abdomen very large, completely overlapping the cephalothorax (Figs 1 & 7); broadly rounded with a very blunt uneven anterior margin (Figs 5–7); ivory-white above, densely and evenly sprinkled with small, round, brown spots, each bearing a tiny setae (Figs 16 & 17); in between with small pitted impressions (Fig. 8); on the posterior edge, with transverse folds forming dark stripes; ventrally dark (Figs 2, 13 & 14). Legs yellowish-brown (Figs 4 & 6). Only the female is known, but a smaller male was photographed at Kloof (Fig. 18).

Variation: The second author provided a series of *P. eburnean* images (Figs 2–6) taken at Kloof in KwaZulu-Natal. It shows how the shape of the abdomen varies from round (Fig. 2) to having a central dorsal hump (Figs. 5–7). The colour of the specimens varies from creamy white to fawn (Figs 4 & 7), with the hump sometimes having a darker tint.

Figures 1–10. *Phoroncidia eburnea*. 1. Female from Delmas. 2–7. Images of specimens photographed at Kloof. 8. Female from Rayton. 8–9. Egg sacs of *P. eburnean*. Credits: 1 & 9. Peter Webb. 2–7 & 9–10. Bruce Blake.

LIFESTYLE

Phoroncidia eburnea is very small and not easily seen. During SANSA surveys, they were sampled by sweeping and beating the vegetation. Research on members of *Phoroncidia* showed that they hunt at night and their webs consist of a single, horizontal sticky silk thread. At Kloof in South Africa, strange egg sacs were observed, always with *P. eburnea* in the vicinity (Figs 9 & 10).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa (Fig. 19).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Ongeluksnek (-30.55, 28.57); Prentjies-berg (-31.18, 28.28); Qachas Nek (-30.12, 28.68); Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97). **Gauteng:** Rayton (-25.74, 28.53). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Garden Castle (-29.75, 29.2); Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72, 32.38); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lhuvhondo Nature reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Goro Game Ranch near Vivo (-22.99, 29.43). **Mpumalanga:** Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87); Kruger National Park: Mopani Tsendze (-23.685, 31.518); Kruger National Park: Pretoriuskop Numbi (-25.140, 31.208); Kruger National Park: Pretoriuskop Shabeni (-25.12, 31.237); Kruger National Park: Satara (-24.399, 31.736); Kruger National Park: Satara (-24.405, 31.766); Kruger National Park: Satara N'wanetsi (-24.448, 31.865); Delmas (-26.146, 28.683). **Northern Cape:** Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.678, 24.304); Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Tswalu Nature Reserve (-27.30, 22.44).

Figure 19. Distribution records of *Phoroncidia eburnea* in South Africa. Showing the SANSA distribution records of material housed in the National Collection of Arachnida and the locations of iNaturalist “Research Grade” observations of *Phoroncidia eburnea* from <https://www.inaturalist.org> exported on 24 September 2025.

HABITAT

Rare spider sampled when sweeping low vegetation. This species has been sampled from the Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011) biomes.

CONSERVATION STATUS

Although only the female is known, the species has a fairly wide distribution and is protected in Benfontein Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad, 2023); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019); Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.* 2008) and Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2018). Males have been collected but still need to be described (Fig. 18).

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